

Review

Empowering electroactive microorganisms for soil remediation: Challenges in the bioelectrochemical removal of petroleum hydrocarbons

Matteo Tucci^{a,1}, Carolina Cruz Viggi^{a,1}, Abraham Esteve Núñez^b, Andrea Schievano^c, Korneel Rabaey^{d,e}, Federico Aulenta^{a,*}

^a Water Research Institute (IRSA), National Research Council (CNR), Monterotondo RM, Italy

^b Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Alcalá, Alcalá de Henares, Madrid, Spain

^c Department of Environmental Science and Policy, e-Bio Center, Università degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy

^d Center for Microbial Ecology and Technology (CMET), Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

^e Center for Advanced Process Technology for Urban Resource Recovery (CAPTURE), Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

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ABSTRACT

Microbial electrochemical technologies (MET) are increasingly being considered for environmental remediation applications, mainly for their unique capability to enhance microbial degradation processes in an environmentally sustainable manner (e.g., without requiring addition of chemicals and with little or even no energy consumption). To date, however, the application of MET for the remediation of saturated and unsaturated soils contaminated by petroleum hydrocarbons (PH) remains challenged by a number of environmental and operational factors which have, so far, hampered a more rapid deployment of the technology. In this context, this critical review has comprehensively analyzed the recent scientific literature dealing with electrobioremediation of PH-contaminated soils, in order to disentangle the impact of key process parameters (e.g., type of electrodes, system configurations, design criteria) and environmental conditions (e.g., soil characteristics and strategies to manipulate thereof, type of contaminants, composition of PH-degrading communities) on the overall remediation performance. Interestingly, the analysis revealed that MET-based soil electrobioremediation has been successfully applied to remove a variety of PH (from alkanes to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and mixtures thereof) from soils displaying a broad range of electric conductivities (0.2–6 mS/cm), using different system configurations (from simple graphite rod buried within soils to more complex tubular electrode assemblies). To date, the limited radius-of-influence of electrodes buried in contaminated soils, which is typically lower than 50 cm, appears to be a main limiting factor which requires specific strategies (e.g., amendment of soil with conductive materials/minerals and/or surfactants) to be properly addressed. Finally, the study highlights the urgent need for pilot-scale testing to confirm the promising results obtained at the laboratory-scale under more controlled, yet often far-less representative, conditions as well as to catalyze the commercial and societal interest towards this novel technology.

1. Introduction

1.1. Soil contamination by petroleum hydrocarbons (PH)

The contamination of soil by petroleum hydrocarbons (PH) is a widespread problem, which poses severe threats to the environment and to the human health due to the harmful nature of these contaminants [1,2]. As an example, based on a recent survey, over one million of potentially contaminated sites have been identified in Europe with PH

being identified as major soil pollutants in nearly 50% of the cases [3]. Although PH may also naturally occur in subsurface environments, contamination is frequently linked to industrial activities (e.g., accidental spills occurring during oil exploration, extraction, processing, utilization, as well as inappropriate disposal practices) [4–6].

On soils, PH permeate vertically downward through the unsaturated zone until they reach the groundwater and spread sideways. Overall, the distribution and fate of PH in subsurface environments largely depend on their physical–chemical and biological properties (e.g., density,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: aulenta@irsa.cnr.it (F. Aulenta).

¹ These authors contributed equally to this work

water solubility, vapor pressure, sorption characteristics, biodegradability, and chemical stability), as well as on soil characteristics (e.g., composition, texture, organic matter and moisture content) [6]. Along this line, PH may dissolve in the pore water, adsorb onto the soil organic matter, partition into the soil gas phase and even remain as separated non-aqueous phase liquids (NAPL) [7,8]. In general, contaminants with higher water solubility, volatility, and biodegradability are not likely to persist in soils for long periods, whereas those with the opposite characteristics will tend to leach out from soils slowly and ultimately become a continuous source of groundwater pollution [4].

1.2. Physico-chemical vs. biological, *in-situ* vs. *ex-situ* remediation technologies

It is essential to remediate contaminated soils in order to preserve animal and plant life, and to protect humans and other species from long-term health threats. Over the last years, the increasing awareness of the prevalence and associated risks of soil contamination by PH, has prompted continued research efforts focused on the development and application of effective and economically viable remediation technologies [9,10].

Strategies to remove PH from contaminated soils typically involve physicochemical and/or biological means. Physicochemical approaches comprise mechanical removal (i.e., excavation of the contaminated soil), soil washing with solvents or surfactants, thermal desorption, electrokinetic removal of contaminants, oxidation or reduction via chemical or electrochemical agents [11,12]. Physical and chemical remediation methods are usually relatively expensive, in some cases have an adverse effect on the residual soil quality and may ultimately cause side pollution effects. Thus, in recent years, less aggressive, more environmentally sustainable, bioremediation methods, which exploit the broad metabolic capabilities of naturally occurring microorganisms have been frequently preferred [13-15]. Both physicochemical and biological soil remediation methods can be applied either *in-situ* or *ex-situ* [16]. Typically, *ex-situ* processes are based on the removal of the contaminated soil and its subsequent treatment in aboveground facilities and plants, whereas *in-situ* processes involve the treatment of the soil without its preliminary removal. In general, *in-situ* treatments are more cost-effective and have a lower environmental impact compared to *ex-situ* treatments, since they do not involve digging and transportation of often huge amounts of soil [17]. On the other hand, *in-situ* treatments are highly site-specific, meaning that the optimal treatment conditions are firmly dependent on the local site characteristics (e.g., soil texture, composition, porosity, permeability) and can be generalized to other sites only with caution. On the other hand, *ex-situ* treatments typically allow gaining a greater control over operating conditions which translates into faster degradation rates. As a consequence of that, *ex-situ* treatments are often the preferred ones whenever rapid intervention actions are required.

Bioremediation is an environmentally friendly and cost-efficient method for the treatment of contaminated soil, whereby soil microorganisms (e.g., bacteria, fungi and yeast), under appropriate redox and environmental conditions, transform PH into harmless end-products via different metabolic pathways [12]. In some cases, physicochemical and biological treatment methods can also be combined, so as to integrate the advantages of each, and in turn maximize the treatment capacity and efficiency.

In general, the overarching goal of bioremediation is to accelerate the removal of contaminants by overcoming the limiting factors of microbial metabolism [11]. These can be:

1. lack of electron donor
2. lack of electron acceptor
3. absence of capable organisms
4. lack of nutrients or other essential elements
5. limitation in bioavailability of the pollutant

Common measures to reach this goal include bioaugmentation with exogenous PH-degrading microorganisms and/or stimulation of indigenous microbial communities with specific amendments (e.g., micro- and macro-nutrients, respiratory electron acceptors), whose availability may rate-limit biodegradation [18,19]. In some cases (e.g., in historically contaminated sites), the low bioavailability of contaminants (e.g., polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons) due to their strong binding onto the soil matrix may also limit the rate and extent of biodegradation, thereby necessitating the addition of surfactants to enhance it [20,21].

As far as the addition of electron acceptors is concerned, oxygen is generally the preferred one due to the intrinsically low cost, unlimited availability, and to the fact that PH aerobic biodegradation typically proceeds at substantially higher rates than under anaerobic conditions. On the other hand, oxygen delivery is an energy-intensive process which may also result in the unwanted stripping of contaminants, thus necessitating the capture and post-treatment of the generated off-gases. Furthermore, since microbial growth yields under aerobic conditions are substantially higher than those reported for anaerobic ones, aerobic bioremediation processes typically require the supply of higher amounts of bioavailable macro- and micro-nutrients, thus resulting in increased treatment costs and potential side contamination effects [22,23].

Although in recent years the anaerobic degradation of PH has been extensively documented, the addition of alternative, water-soluble respiratory electron acceptors, such as nitrate or sulfate, may also turn impractical due to the high costs of these chemicals and the stringent regulatory issues related to their use, particularly *in-situ*.

More in general, regardless the type of electron acceptor involved in PH degradation, state-of-the-art bioremediation technologies also typically suffer from the lack of tools capable of providing operators with real-time information on microbial activity and process performance. These latter are instead usually based on data generated from complex, time-consuming, and expensive analyses (e.g., chemical, microbiological or biomolecular) carried on soil samples by specialized laboratories.

1.3. Microbial electrochemical technologies (METs): principles, electrode reactions, and applications

Since it was first observed that microorganisms of *Geobacteraceae* family present in marine sediments were able to produce electricity via direct extracellular electron transfer [24], microbial electrochemical technologies (METs) have increasingly emerged as innovative systems capable to overcome some of the limitations of state-of-the-art bioremediation approaches [25].

METs employ electro-active microorganisms [26] to electro-catalyze oxidation or reduction reactions using solid-state electrodes as virtually inexhaustible electron acceptors or donors, respectively [27,28]. In a MET, electro-active microorganisms use an anode as a respiratory electron acceptor during the oxidation of reduced organic or inorganic compounds (i.e., the metabolic electron donors) (Fig. 1). Upon oxidation of the electron donor, electrons flow from the anode to the cathode (via a conductive material or wire) whereby they are consumed by biotic or abiotic reactions for the reduction of an oxidized compound [29] (Fig. 1). At the same time, the generated protons migrate towards the cathode, thus balancing the charge and participating in the cathodic reduction. In this way, microorganisms convert chemical energy (i.e., stored in the electron donor) into electrical energy which, in principle, can also be used to power a load, as it happens in a microbial fuel cell (MFC). In some cases, however, the electron flow from the anode to the cathode is constrained by thermodynamic or kinetic limitations and an external power supply is required to drive the redox reaction at sufficient rates. Several researchers have shown that an optimum anode potential should be maintained to guarantee efficient MET performance and sustained anodic oxidation rates [30,31]. This can be performed with a 3-electrode MET in which the working electrode potential (in this case for optimum anodic potentials) is controlled by the operator using a potentiostat and a reference electrode. Here, this MET is referred to as a

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the main components of a MET-based electrobioremediation system. Pollutant removal mechanisms: 1) direct electricity-generating oxidation; 2) cooperative electrogenic oxidation; 3) adsorption; 4) electromigration and other electrokinetic transport mechanisms; 5) direct electricity-consuming reduction.

microbial 3-electrode cell (M3C). Clearly, this approach may suffer from difficulties with maintaining a set working electrode potential for large surface areas [32]. In certain MET configurations, a separator is placed between the anode and the cathode to prevent short circuit between the electrodes and/or limit the migration of substrates among electrodes compartments while permitting the movement of charged species, thus ensuring the electroneutrality (Fig. 1).

Interestingly, from a bioremediation perspective, environmental pollutants may serve as either anodic electron donors (e.g., oxidizable PH) or cathodic electron acceptors (e.g., reducible chlorinated solvents) (Fig. 1) [33]. In general, the most relevant mechanisms responsible for contaminants removal and degradation in MET-based electrobioremediation systems include: i. direct anodic oxidation of reduced contaminants like PH all the way to carbon dioxide and water [13]; ii. cooperative oxidation driven by syntrophic communities whereby the contaminant is initially converted into simpler molecules (e.g., fermentation products such as acetate and hydrogen), with these latter being subsequently oxidized at the electrode by electro-active species [34]; iii. sorption, whereby contaminants are adsorbed onto the surface of the electrodes or within the biofilm colonizing the electrodes [28]; iv. electrokinetic removal, whereby the chemical speciation and distribution of soil contaminants is influenced by the applied electric current [35,36]; v. cathodic reduction, whereby oxidized contaminants (e.g., halogenated organics, nitroaromatics, azo dyes, high-valent metals) are reduced consuming electrons generated from the anode [37-41]. Clearly, depending on the type of contaminants and the reaction conditions, a combination of different remediation mechanisms can occur. For example, in a soil microcosm study, toluene and benzene were rapidly sorbed onto the surface of a carbon-based anode prior to being anaerobically oxidized with the electrode serving as terminal electron acceptor [28].

In comparison with traditional remediation techniques, MET can offer several advantages, like: i. the microbial electrochemical process typically uses much less energy relative to other chemical or physical

approaches; ii. whenever produced, the generated electricity can power remote indicators or wireless sensors, exploitable for monitoring purposes; iii. METs can stimulate both oxidation and reduction reactions, thus allowing the establishment of versatile treatment trains, and in turn permitting the removal of complex mixtures of contaminants [42,43].

Despite such promising technical and scientific characteristics, the actual potential of MET for soil remediation has not been fully demonstrated yet, primarily due to an often-limited understanding of the technical and operational factors influencing process performance.

In this context, the main focus of this critical review is to analyze the most recent scientific literature dealing with electrobioremediation of PH-contaminated soils, in order to disentangle the impact of the different process parameters and environmental conditions on the overall performance. The final aim is to contribute to the definition of design criteria which may drive the transition of such a novel technology from the laboratory to the market.

1.4. Direct vs. Mediated extracellular electron transfer

The direct electron transfer between a microorganism and an insoluble acceptor or donor involves the physical contact of the microbial cell redox-active component with the MET electrode. Direct extracellular electron transfer mechanisms were first discovered in sediment bacteria like *Geobacter* species, which were shown to transfer metabolic electrons to an anode using the same mechanism used for the reduction of iron(III) oxides or syntrophic partner organisms in their natural environment [44]. Despite the fact that direct electron transfer is ascribed to several well-known sediments inhabiting microorganisms like *Geobacter*, *Rhodferax* and *Shewanella*, the underlying molecular mechanisms are still subject of intense investigations. As an example, recently, it has been demonstrated that some *Geobacter* and *Shewanella* strains can evolve electronically conducting molecular pili, denominated as nanowires, that allow the microorganism to reach and utilize more distant solid electron acceptors without physical whole cell contact [45,46]. It has

been speculated that such nanowires may allow the development of thicker electroactive biofilms and thus higher anode performances although intense debates on the specific structure and conductivity of these elements are ongoing.

Mediated electron transfer represents an effective means to wire the microbial metabolism to an anode or cathode without a physical contact between the microbial cell and the electrode [47]. Mediated electron transfer relies on soluble electron-shuttling compounds which can be reversibly oxidized and reduced. These compounds can thus carry electrons between microbial cells and insoluble electron acceptors or donors, thereby enabling long-distance electron transfer. As the oxidation and reduction of electron-shuttling compounds are reversible, small catalytic amounts can undergo multiple reduction–oxidation cycles. Several different compounds were reported to function as redox mediators in MET including organic and inorganic, as well as natural and synthetic molecules. Humic substances that contain quinone moieties were the first electron-shuttling compounds reported to stimulate anode or Fe(III) oxide reduction. To date it has been shown that *Shewanella* spp. *Pseudomonas* spp. and other bacteria can release flavins as electron shuttles [48].

Importantly, it was demonstrated that the (direct and mediated) electron transfer kinetics and thermodynamics of electrochemically active microorganisms can be assessed by the use of dynamic electrochemical methods, such as cyclic voltammetry [49].

2. Electrode types: materials, geometry and surface functionalization

2.1. Anode materials

To date, carbon-based materials are by far the most commonly used to build the anodes of MET (Table 1), primarily due to their low cost, good electrical conductivity ($>10^3$ S/m), biocompatibility and corrosion resistance [50]. These materials can have either a 2D or a 3D spatial arrangement. The 2D electrodes are preferable when a well-defined surface area is needed (e.g., proof of concept and/or kinetic studies). Some examples of this group are carbon cloth, carbon mesh, carbon felt and graphite rods [51]. On the contrary, materials like carbon brushes, carbon fiber cylinders, graphite granules and biochar can be used as 3D electrodes [52], which offer remarkably higher surface area for the colonization of electro-active biofilms [53]. For this reason, they typically result in higher rates of contaminant removal and typically better remediation capabilities.

Biochar, a charcoal-like product obtained from pyrolysis (>400 °C) of lignocellulosic substances, is another interesting material to be employed in MET-based electrobioremediation processes [52,54]. Even though it is fairly new on this specific application, biochar is already well-known in the literature for its environmental functions: soil amendment to enhance water and nutrient retention capabilities [55], or soil additive for contaminant sequestration [56,57]. The relatively low cost of the material and ease of application make it suitable for a number of soil remediation applications [18]. Despite the commercial biochars may have relatively low electrical conductivity (<50 S/m), biochar has been reported to exchange electrons with microbes as well as to function as an electron conduit during microbe-to-microbe interspecies electron transfer processes, primarily due to the presence of redox-active functional groups on its surface which have a broad range of formal redox potentials [52,58–60]. In principle, this interesting feature could be exploited to link microbially-catalyzed redox processes taking place in the bulk of soil to spatially distant electrodes, so as to extend the radius-of-influence of an electrode buried within a contaminated soil and in turn to enhance the performance of an electrobioremediation process. A preliminary confirmation of this hypothesis has been reported by Cai et al. [61] who demonstrated that the radius of influence of pentachlorophenol degradation in a MET was highly increased by the presence of biochar. The analysis of the microbial

communities confirmed the presence of bacteria-biochar networks as well as the enrichment of *Desulfitobacterium* and *Geobacter* in the biochar-amended MET system. In agreement with the above-mentioned relevant capacity of biochar to engage in electron transfer processes with microbes, Lu et al. recently reported no significant difference in TPH biodegradation when granular graphite or biochar were used as anodes in a column-type MET, in spite of the substantially lower electrical conductivity of the latter, ultimately confirming that factors other than the electrical conductivity may play a role in MET-based electrobioremediation processes [18].

In another study an even higher current peak was obtained with a biochar anode as compared to a carbon cloth anode. According to the authors, this finding was attributed to the higher adsorption capability of the biochar relative to the carbon cloth, which possibly resulted in a higher local concentration of hydrocarbons to the electroactive biofilm [55].

In another experiment, Li et al. compared the effect of three different types of biochar on the MET-based degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons [62]. They observed that the removal of PH increased in the presence of biochar, with interesting variations between the different types of biochar used: the one obtained from chicken manure yielded the best alkanes removal, possibly due to the higher content of bioavailable minerals such as phosphorus which may have stimulated the microbial metabolism, whereas the biochar obtained from wheat straw improved the removal of aromatics, possibly due to its higher molecular polarity. On the contrary, the worst performances were obtained with the biochar obtained from wood sawdust, possibly due to strong adsorption of the contaminants on the material and their diminished bioavailability. Indeed, the interplay between sorption and bioavailability remains a critical yet unresolved issue which certainly warrants further investigations [63]. Taken as whole, however, these studies suggest that biochar is a highly versatile electrode material whose bulk and surface chemical and electrochemical characteristics and physical properties can be fine-tuned (e.g., using feedstocks of different composition and/or applying different pyrolysis conditions) in order to obtain products for tailored MET-based electrobioremediation applications.

2.2. Functionalization of the electrode surface

One effective method to further improve the performance of MET-based bioremediation processes is to modify the anodic surface [67]. The ultimate goal is to favor the enrichment of electroactive bacteria capable to degrade the target pollutants and/or to enhance the electron transfer rates [81,82]. Carbon nanomaterials are ideal candidates for anode functionalization, due to their high surface area-to-volume ratios, high conductivity and excellent electrochemical characteristics. Examples of these materials are carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene (GR) and graphene oxides (GO) [67]. In a recent study, Liang et al. [67] demonstrated that anodes modified with these materials enhanced the electrochemically active surface area, the amount of attached biomass and the microbial diversity of the anodic biofilm, thus effectively enhancing the generation of electricity and the removal rates of phenanthrene and pyrene.

In spite of these promising results, surface functionalization as a strategy to improve electrobioremediation performances has been, so far, investigated almost exclusively at laboratory scale under non-fully representative environmental conditions. Furthermore, a technical, economical, and ecotoxicological assessment of the practical viability and sustainability of this approach for field applications is still missing.

To date, there are other methods of surface functionalization that have been successfully tested to enhance the performances of METs, like controlling of the micro and nanoscale topography, incorporating functional groups, employing conductive polymers, or doping with transition metals [83]. These techniques have never been applied specifically to soil bioremediation, but they may still be viable strategies to be studied in the future. For example, micro and nanoscale surface

Table 1
Overview of recent MET-based soil remediation studies.

Reactor setup		Experimental conditions				Performance			Ref.
Anodic material	Reactor type and size	Pollutant	Inoculum	Soil type	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Initial PH concentration	Removal %	Operational time (d)	
Carbon based materials	Single chamber (1.12 L)	Synthetic wastewater	Anodic biofilm pre-enriched on PH-containing wastewater	Saturated peat moss - soil (70:30)	N.R.	TPH = 320 – 840 mg/L	39.9% – 45.83%	14–21	[64]
Carbon cloth	Column-type (1.06 L)	PH	PH- contaminated soil	Saturated soil	5.45 ± 0.07	TPH = 83 ± 0.3 g/kg; Alk. = 49 ± 0.6 g/kg; Arom. = 28 ± 0.3 g/kg	TPH = 11.1 ± 1.4%; Alk. = 17.0 ± 1.9%; Arom. = 24.5 ± 3.3%	182	[65]
Carbon mesh	U-tube (2.7 L)	PH	PH-contaminated soil	Saline soil: sand 24%; coarse silt 30%; fine silt 22%; coarse clay 14%; fine clay 10%	8.32	TPH = 28.3 g/kg	TPH = 15.2 ± 0.6%; Alk. = 79%; Arom. = 42%	25	[13]
Graphite rod	Single chamber (0.72 L)	PH	PH-contaminated soil	Saturated soil:sand 30%; coarse 23%; silt 25%	1.99	Alk. = 0.7 ± 0.04 g/Kg; Arom. = 7.9 ± 0.5 mg/kg	TPHs = 30 ± 1%; Alk. = 55 ± 2%; Arom. = 33–45%	144	[66]
Graphite felt (GF) as such or modified with: graphene (GR); graphene oxide (GO); carbon nanotubes (CNTs)	Column-type (0.58 L)	Phenanthrene and pyrene (spiked)	Sediment	Saturated lake sediment	N.R.	Phenanthrene = 1.23 mg/Kg; Pyrene = 1.15 mg/kg	Phenanthrene:CNTs = 78.1%; GR = 73%; GO = 71.2%; GF = 45.6%; Pyrene: GO = 69.6%; GR = 68.2%; CNT = 66.7%; GF = 42.3%	110	[67]
Carbon felt	Column-type	Diesel (spiked)	Diesel -contaminated soil	Soil mixed with quartz sand and clay powder to form artificial Sandy Soil (SS) and Clayey Soil (CS)	Sandy soil = 0.542 ± 0.023; Clayey soil = 1.121 ± 0.017	TPH (SS) = 6.96 ± 0.10 g/kg; TPH (CS) = 6.495 ± 0.115 g/kg	TPH (SS): 48–59%; TPH (CS): 42–45%	250	[68]
Carbon mesh	Multi-anode (0.324 L)	PH	PH-contaminated soil	Saturated aged soil (mixed with Glucose solution 0.1% w/v)	1.99	N.R.	TPH = 21%; Arom.: = 38–44%; Alk.: = 46–53%	135	[69]
Carbon cloth	Column-type (0.1 L)	PH	PH-contaminated sediment	Saturated sandy marine sediment (sand 52.3%, silt 30.5%, clay 17.2%)	4.54	TPH = 18.75 g/kg	TPH = 24.4%	66	[70]
Graphite granules or Biochar	Column-type (50 L)	Diesel	Diesel-contaminated soil	Saturated sandy loam (sand 61.83%, silt 20.62%, clay 17.55%)	3.09 ± 0.06	TPH = 12.25 ± 0.36 g/kg	TPH = 82.1–89.7%	120	[18]
Graphite rod	Single chamber (0.15L)	Dibenzothiophene (DBT)	DBT-contaminated soil	Saturated HaplicFluvisol (Calcaric) soil (sand 30%, silt 19%, clay 32%)	50	DBT = 0.5 mg/kg	51%	21	[71]
Carbon mesh	Multi-anode (0.324 L)	PH	PH-contaminated soil	Saline soil	1.994	TPH = 25.7 g/kg	TPH = 12%; Alk. = 29%; Arom. = 27%	180	[72]
Carbon felt	Column-type (4.4 L)	Diesel	Diesel-contaminated soil	Saturated sandy soil (SS): 57.14% sand, 28.93% silt and 13.93% clay; Saturated clayey soil (CS): 33.12% sand, 35.46% silt, 31.42% clay	sandy soil = 2.2; clayey soil = 5.1	TPH = 6.96 g/kg (SS); 6.49 g/kg (CS)	TPH (SS): 39%-41%; TPH (CS): 25%-35%	230	[73]
Carbon mesh	Multi-anode (0.324 L)	PH	PH-contaminated soil	Saturated soil	1.99	TPH = 25.7 g/kg	TPH = 12.5%; Arom. = 14%; Alk. = 22%	135	[74]

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Reactor setup		Experimental conditions					Performance		Ref.
Anodic material	Reactor type and size	Pollutant	Inoculum	Soil type	Conductivity (mS/cm)	Initial PH concentration	Removal %	Operational time (d)	
Carbon mesh + Biochar	Single chamber (0.216 L)	PH	PH-contaminated soil	Saturated soil	N.R.	TPH = 64.2 ± 0.9 g/kg; Alk. = 38.1 ± 0.8 g/kg; Arom.: = 17.0 ± 0.6 g/kg	TPH = 42%; Alk. = 34%; Arom. = 44%	223	[62]
Carbon cloth anode (CCA) or Biochar anode (BCA)	Column-type (3 L)	PH	Diesel-contaminated soil	Saturated soil	3.4 (CCA); 3.3 (BCA)	TPH = 11.5 ± 0.6 g/kg	TPH (BCA): 56.8%-78.7%; TPH (CCA): 51.5%-73.1%	64	[55]
Carbon felt	Column-type (4.8 L)	PH	PH contaminated soil	Saturated sandy soil (Sand = 69.4% Silt = 20.0% Clay = 10.6%)	0.61 ± 0.01	TPH = 11.34 ± 3.26 g/kg	TPH: 23%-37%	110	[75]
Carbon mesh	Single chamber (0.324 L)	PH	PH contaminated soil	Saturated soil	Rinsed salt (RS) = 0.61; Carbon fiber + rinsed salt (RM) = 1.51; Carbon fiber (MC) = 1.33; Original soil (OS) = 1.81	N.R.	TPH = 60 ± 9%; Arom. = 44–88%; Alk = 59–92%	65	[76]
Carbon mesh	Multi-anode	PH	PH contaminated soil	Saturated Low sand (LS) 5:1 and High sand (HS) 2:1, (mass ratios soil to sand, w/w)	Control = 1.52 ± 0.03; LS = 1.40 ± 0.19; HS = 1.10 ± 0.19	TPH = 25.7 g/kg	TPH = 22.0 ± 0.5%; Arom. = 48%; Alk. = 54 ± 8%	135	[77]
Carbon mesh	Single chamber (0.261 L)	PH	PH contaminated soil	Saturated soil	lecithos (LEC) = 1.13; sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) = 0.35; β-cyclodextrin (CYC) = 0.9; cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) = 0.62	N.R.	TPH (LEC): 77 ± 2%; TPH (SDS): 56 ± 1%; TPH (CYC): 50 ± 1%; TPH (CTAB): 27 ± 1%	182	[78]
Carbon felt	Column-type (4.8 L)	Diesel	PH contaminated soil	Saturated sandy soil (clay loam and sand, 1:1) with polyacrylamide hydrogel (SHB)	0.61 ± 0.01	TPH = 11.34 ± 3.26 g/kg	TPH (SHB): 30–44%	110	[75]
Carbon fibre brush	Dual chamber (0.3 L each chamber)	PH	PH contaminated soil	Saturated soil (Sand = 65.05%, Silt = 28.19%, Clay = 6.73%)	0.486	TPH = 0.024 g/kg dry soil	TPH = 37.5 ± 6.3%; Alk. = 27–45%	137	[79]
Graphite felt	Column-type (4.7 L)	benzo[a]pyrene (BaP)	Soil	Saturated soil	N.R.	BaP: 1.55 ± 0.09 mg/kg	BaP: 52.52 ± 4.23%	50	[80]

Legend. N.R.: Not Reported. TPH: Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons. Alk.: Alkanes. Arom.: Aromatic hydrocarbons.

topography has been identified as a key feature impacting the performance of electroactive biofilm in terms of formation, bacterial adhesion, and electron transfer reactions [84]. As a matter of fact, several works reported that micro-structured electrodes can greatly enhance the current generation in MFCs [85-87]. Another surface functionalization method consists in the attachment of functional groups to the carbon electrode. Katuri et al. [88] reported that hydrophilic groups (i.e., $-\text{NH}_2$, $-\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{OH}$) enhance early-stage biofilm formation. Moreover, according to Saito et al. [89] the addition of nitrogen-containing functional groups on a carbon cloth anode can improve the power production in MFCs. Finally, conductive polymers like polyaniline, polypyrrole, polyallylamine, and poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) have also been widely employed to modify carbon-based electrodes in microbial electrochemical systems [90], having positive impacts on the current generation and biofilm stability. The different functionalization methods are summarized in Fig. 2.

3. Microbial communities and related metabolic interactions involved in PH degradation

In soil electrobioremediation, as in any microbial bioprocess, the community composition plays a pivotal role in shaping treatment performance, efficiency, and reliability. This is, even to a greater extent, the case of PH whose electricity-driven anaerobic biodegradation often relies on complex syntrophic and/or cooperative interactions among community members [34,91]. The microbiology of anaerobic PH biodegradation has been comprehensively reviewed in previous papers [92,93], which have also specifically addressed the existing correlations between target microbial groups and PH-degradation efficiencies. Here, three different anaerobic biodegradation scenarios, which are relevant to MET-based soil bioremediation, are presented (Fig. 3) and discussed. The first scenario involves the direct bioelectrocatalytic oxidation of PH by electroactive bacteria. In this case, a single electroactive microorganism is responsible for the initial PH activation and the subsequent oxidation, with the electrode serving as the terminal respiratory electron acceptor (Fig. 3). This mechanism has been, so far, experimentally demonstrated only for a restricted number of microbial species, mainly iron-reducers, and only simple hydrocarbon molecules. As an example,

the model electro-active microorganism *Geobacter metallireducens* has been reported to catalyze the complete electrogenic oxidation of monoaromatic hydrocarbons such as benzene, phenol, and toluene [27]. This finding was confirmed by Palma et al., who reported, in recent studies, the enrichment of *Geobacter* sp. at graphite bioanodes fed with groundwater contaminated by phenol, toluene, or a BTEX mixture and identified the involved PH activation pathways [94-97].

In a second scenario (Fig. 2), the biodegradation of PH is driven by the syntrophic cooperation of non-electroactive and electroactive *Bacteria* [34]. Following an activation step, typically proceeding via fumarate addition, carboxylation or hydroxylation [98,99], non-electroactive fermentative microorganisms catalyze the partial oxidation of PH to CO_2/H_2 , acetate or a mixture thereof. Such reactions are, however, largely endergonic under standard biochemical conditions which in turn forces these microorganisms to rely on the activity of electroactive bacteria, such as *Geobacter* species, to rapidly oxidize the produced H_2 and acetate with the electrode serving as terminal electron acceptor, thereby making the overall reaction energetically favorable. Frequently, PH-degrading fermentative bacteria and electroactive microorganisms feeding on acetate and H_2 are intimately associated one to each other within anodic biofilms. However, the discovery of long-distance interspecies electron transfer, mediated by e.g., conductive minerals such as iron oxides or even filamentous "cable" bacteria [100] raises the possibility that such syntrophic biodegradation processes may take place even when the fermentative and the electro-active partners are spatially separated, yet electrically connected [91,101,102]. This intriguing hypothesis is at least partially supported by the observation that addition of conductive particles (or biochar) to PH-contaminated soils have the potential to extend the radius-of-influence of electrodes in MET-based soil bioremediation processes.

Finally, a third scenario (Fig. 3) highlights the role of sulfate-reducing bacteria as the PH-degrading microorganisms. In this case, the reaction takes place in the bulk of the soil, while the anode catalyzes the biotic and/or abiotic back-oxidation of sulfide (i.e., the end-product of sulfate reduction) into sulfate, and by so doing continuously regenerates the metabolic electron acceptor. Furthermore, the electrode reaction also prevents the accumulation of sulfide which is known to inhibit the metabolism of sulfate-reducing bacteria. This mechanism has

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of surface and bulk anode functionalization strategies.

Fig. 3. Schematic overview of possible microbial interactions in soil electrobioremediation systems: A) direct bioelectrocatalytic oxidation of PH; B) bioelectrocatalytic oxidation of PH driven by the cooperative/syntrophic metabolism of fermentative and electroactive bacteria; C) sulfate-driven oxidation of PH linked to (bio)electrocatalytic oxidation of sulfide to sulfate.

been extensively documented in the case for PH-contaminated sediments and has also been suggested to play a role in contaminated aquifers [101,103,104]. On the other hand, its relevance to PH-contaminated soils still needs to be ascertained. Overall, despite the ever-increasing understanding of the microbial interactions occurring in MET-based soil bioremediation systems, practical strategies to manipulate thereof, in the sake of an improved treatment efficacy and long-term reliability are still limited and warrants further investigation.

4. Relevance of soil characteristics on MET-based bioremediation

Soil properties are found to be determinant factors in MET-based bioremediation processes. Common influencing features include soil type and texture, water content, electrical conductivity, salinity, type of contamination, presence of additives.

4.1. Electrical conductivity, water content, texture, salinity

Electrical conductivity is a measure of the ability of a soil to conduct an electrical current [51]. Electrical conductivity is intimately related to a number of factors, among which stand out the water content, the soil

texture and the salinity [51,73]. A low electrical conductivity of soils is one of the primary factors commonly limiting electrobioremediation performance [105]. Indeed, sluggish electron and ion transfer capabilities hinder electricity production and lead to significantly decreased microbial electrochemical activities along with distance.

Since large internal resistance inhibits the performance of MET-based processes, minimizing soil resistivity by adding silica [106] or sand [77] is therefore a key to improve soil electrobioremediation performance.

Increasing water content, up to saturation conditions, may be a strategy to reduce the resistivity of soil [51]. Wang and colleagues in U-tube microbial fuel cells increased the initial water content from 23% to 28 and 33%. The increase of soil moisture resulted in a decrease of the internal resistance from 42.6Ω (23% water content) to 7.4Ω (33% water content), and consequently an increase of the electrical conductivity from 8.36 ± 0.59 mS/cm (23% water content) to 13.4 ± 2.3 mS/cm (33% water content). This corresponded to an improvement in performance in terms of charge output and hydrocarbon degradation rate [13]. In another study, the impact of different water contents (20 – 48%) and textures (sandy or clay soil) on the bioelectrochemical remediation of hydrocarbon-contaminated soils was evaluated [68]. High water saturation level enhanced the bioelectrochemical

remediation, in both sandy and clay soil texture. Anyway, the effect was more marked in sandy soils. At the end of the experiment with saturated soils, 48–59% of TPH were removed close to the anode in sandy soils and 42–45% in clay soils, which was about 20–48% and 45–55% higher than that from open circuit controls, respectively. For unsaturated soils, TPH removal was enhanced of 17% (clay soil) and 12% (sandy soil) with respect to controls.

Overall, a detailed analysis of the scientific literature revealed that most of the studies concerning hydrocarbons bioremediation in MET-based systems were carried out in saturated soil conditions in order to assure the ionic contact between anode and cathode [72,74,107]. Recently, Domínguez and Núñez reported a new lab-scale configuration by integrating an out-of-soil cathodic chamber with a ceramic barrier so that a closed-circuit system could be achieved without flooding the soil, as shown in Fig. 4 [108]. As proof of concept, this configuration was used to enhance the bioelectrochemical removal of atrazine from a polluted soil: >98% of the initially available atrazine was efficiency removed after 2 weeks of treatment. These results indicate the feasibility of applying electrobioremediation technologies to unsaturated soil.

More recently, the implementation of a moisture retention layer (thickness: 2 cm) around column-type MFC was proposed to enhance soil remediation under unsaturated conditions [75]. This study demonstrated that mixing low-cost polyacrylamide hydrogel in the soil layer close to the bioanode greatly enhanced TPH degradation and current generation as compared to soil-only controls. Thus, this technique may improve hydrocarbon remediation in the vadose zone.

In addition to moisture, resistivity in soils is mainly due to the high density of clay and inorganic compounds complexes of different sizes, which act as barrier for ions and substrates migrating towards the electrodes and, concomitantly, waste products migrating away from the electrodes [13]. In addition, the presence in soil of viscous and hydrophobic oil contaminants can aggravate this transport problem.

As already seen, for a given water content, sandy soil typically showed a better bioremediation performance than clay soil in terms of TPH removed [68]. Sandy soil was mainly constituted by sand, followed by silt and clay ($57.14 \pm 0.03\%$ sand; $28.93 \pm 0.06\%$ silt; $13.93 \pm 0.05\%$ clay). In clay soil, the three constituents were present approximately at the same percentages ($33.12 \pm 0.08\%$ sand; $35.46 \pm 0.06\%$ silt; $31.42 \pm 0.04\%$ clay). The best performance in saturated sandy soil reactors can be attributed to better mass transfer properties due to the increase in porosity, though electrical conductivity of clay soil was nearly twice as much that of the sandy soil ($1121 \pm 17 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and $542 \pm 23 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$,

respectively) (Wang et al., 2019). Indeed, even though conductivity seems to improve microbial electron transfer reactions, this factor alone does not guarantee successful removal.

Generally, a higher hydraulic conductivity the soil matrix is associated to better degradation performances [105]. With permeable sand soil a higher removal efficiency of hydrocarbons and larger radius of influence were observed, as compared to clay soil [73]. After 60 day of operation, the electrified reactor with sand soil removed 41% of contaminants at 5 cm from the reactor and 35% at 39 cm, while the reactor with clay soil removed only 23% and 17% of contaminants at 5 and 39 cm, respectively.

Li and co-authors mixed sand with soil contaminated by PH to accelerate the transport of ions and substrates [77]. The study demonstrated that addition of sand reduced inherent resistance, promoted ion and substrate transport in soil MFCs, and hence improved electricity generation and remediation performance. Therefore, sand can be used as an effective amendment to increase power output and accelerate pollutant removal from soils.

A well-consolidated method employed to reduce the internal resistance of MET for (waste)water treatment is increasing ion concentration of the solution [109]. Similarly, this approach could be transferred to soil electrobioremediation systems. A previous study showed that adding sodium chloride to a sediment improved its electrical conductivity, and consequently the performance of the MFC [110]. However, for actual polluted soil, the addition of exogenous salts could increase the cost of the treatment, and also result in soil salinization. Furthermore, while contaminated saline-alkali soils show a fairly high electrical conductivity, it is important to underline that high salinity is harmful to most microorganisms [51]. In fact, the high osmotic pressure caused by high salinity inhibits the activity of indigenous microorganisms, and consequently hinders their ability to degrade pollutants [111,112]. In a previous study for example, a decrease of the soluble salt content in the soil from 2.86 to 0.10% enhanced the degradation rate of TPHs by 30% [111].

Therefore, in some cases a certain number of measures have been taken to desalinate soil, in order to reduce the salt stress before establishing soil electrobioremediation, such as irrigation and leaching [76]. In particular, the study of Li and colleagues evidenced that the degradation rate of rinsed soil was about 150% higher with respect to original soil. The enhancement was attributed to the stimulated growth of soil microbial community when salinity was reduced. However, the inherent resistance of soil was enhanced by 138% after rinsed in water [76]. Desalination is bound to reduce the electrical conductivity of soil, which thus needs to be considered comprehensively.

4.2. Soil amendments and additives

The biodegradation of PH can be stimulated through the addition of micro- and macro-nutrients and electron acceptors, which are often present at rate-limiting concentrations in PH-contaminated soils. The impact of such additives on conventional bioremediation processes has been extensively reviewed elsewhere [19]. Hereafter, the impact of electrically conductive additives on PH electrobioremediation is specifically analyzed. Indeed, an increasing number of studies have suggested that electricity generation in soil electrobioremediation systems can be increased through the addition of conductive materials like carbon fiber and biochar [62,66,76,78]. In principle, considering that biochar application in agriculture is a rather established practice [113], it can be anticipated that addition of other conductive (solid) additives to soils, in order to improve electrobioremediation efficiency, could be based on similar procedures, provided the materials to be used have physical and mechanical properties comparable to those of biochar.

Carbon fiber is the most used amendment in MET-based systems for soil remediation [66,76,78]. The mixed carbon fiber apparently enhanced the bioelectricity generation and remediation efficiency by means of promoting the electron transfer rate from the electro-active

Fig. 4. A) and B) Configuration of the system proposed by Domínguez and Núñez: 1- Cathodic chamber; 2- cathode-graphite felt; 3- ceramic cone that serves as interface between anode and cathode; 4- anode-carbon fiber cylinder; 5- polluted soil. C) Scheme of the bioelectrochemical degradation of atrazine [108].

bacteria to the soil and the anode. As previously mentioned, decreasing the resistance, especially the current transfer resistance, is vital to the performance of bioelectrochemical remediation system. When carbon fibers are mixed with original contaminated soil (1% w/w, dry weight), the maximum current density, the maximum power density and the accumulated charge output of MFC were 10, 22 and 16 times as high as those of closed-circuit control (without additives), while the internal resistance of microbial cell reduced by 58%. The degradation rates of total petroleum hydrocarbons was enhanced by 100% and 329% compared to closed and opened circuit controls without the carbon fiber, respectively [66]. Other studies involved the use of carbon fiber (2% w/w) in combination with surfactants [78] and soil rinsing [76] to increase the performance of the bioelectrochemical remediation.

The removal of PH and electricity generation were enhanced also by addition of biochar [62]. However, Li *et al.* reported that 79–86% of the total charge output from biochar-amended contaminated soils was generated after 5 months, indicating that the enhancement of biochar on the degradation and electricity production needs a long-term process. Biochar with different physicochemical properties gave different bioremediation performances and influenced the colonized microbial communities of bacteria and archaea [62]. In a recent study, Cai *et al.* demonstrated that the degradation rate of pentachlorophenol with bioelectrochemical system was up to sevenfold higher when the soil was amended with biochar [61]. Moreover, biochar quadrupled the radius of influence of the system, from 4 cm to 16 cm, by creating conductive networks that increased the electron transfer rate. These results indicate that biochar can effectively enhance the electrobioremediation of polluted soils.

4.3. “Fresh” vs. “Aged” soil contamination

The bioremediation performance of a given MET also largely depends on the type and “history” of soil contamination. Many published lab-scale studies on PH-electrobioremediation were carried out using “aged” contaminated soils (i.e., soils subjected to years-long contamination) [13,55,61,62,66,69,72,74–78,107]. A number of studies have tested soils “freshly” spiked (often directly in the laboratory) with diesel oil [18,68,71]. Generally, the higher degradability of diesel compared to aged petroleum yielded better bioremediation performances [69,105].

In general, soils contaminated by aged PH suffer from the scarcity of metabolic electron acceptors, the limited bioavailability of contaminants, the low activity of functional microbes and inefficient electron transfer, with all of these factors hindering the bioremediation application [78]. In MET-based systems, strategies to overcome these limitations may imply the supplementation of exogenous carbon source [69] and the use of surfactants [78]. As an example, when glucose was added as co-substrate for simultaneous electricity generation and petroleum hydrocarbon degradation in air–cathode MFCs, the charge output of SMFC was enhanced by 262%, and the total petroleum hydrocarbon degradation rate increased by 200% with respect to the control [69]. The addition of a readily hydrolysable carbon source (e.g. glucose) can bring about rapid acclimation of electroactive bacteria and higher hydrocarbon degradation rates.

Li and colleagues tested five kinds of surfactants containing bio-surfactants, cationic, anionic, ampholytic and nonionic surfactants to enhance electrobioremediation of aged PH-contaminated soil [78]. They found that the ampholytic (i.e. lecithos), anionic surfactants (i.e. sodium dodecyl sulfate) and biosurfactants (i.e. β -cyclodextrin) are more suitable for bioelectricity generation and hydrocarbon degradation, while nonionic (i.e. glyceryl monostearate) and cationic (i.e. cetyltrimethylammonium bromide) surfactants were less effective.

5. System configurations

5.1. Design and geometry

In order to address the many issues related to the application of METs to soil remediation from PHs, different configurations have been proposed over the years. Up to now, 6 main types of reactors can be found in literature: A) insertion-type, B) tubular or column-type, C) U-type, D) multi-anode, and E) graphite rod (Fig. 5).

It can be observed how all of these systems are air–cathode MFCs. This is probably because they represent the most feasible and cost effective strategy in view of a field application, since they do not consume energy and use molecular oxygen from the atmosphere as ultimate electron acceptor [51].

The first MET-based device to be developed consisted in an insertion-type MFC (Fig. 5A) that was constructed and inserted into waterlogged paddy soil to enhance the removal of organic pollutants using phenol as a model pollutant [114]. A layer of carbon felt served as the anode, while a cloth cathode assembly was fabricated from a piece of GORE-TEX® cloth. This tubular insertion-type air–cathode, based on a simple cylinder configuration, enhanced phenol degradation six-fold compared to a control. This pioneering work demonstrated the viability of using MFCs for bioremediation of soils contaminated by hydrocarbons and laid the foundation for further studies.

Subsequently, tubular [55,68] and column-type [18,75] air–cathode MET-based systems were applied to remediate soil contaminated by PH (Fig. 5B). Both configurations were similar to that of the insertion-type soil MFC. Typical tubular and column type reactors are constructed in soil remediation by wrapping an assembly of anode, separator and cathode layers around a tube. The cathode layer faces the inside and is exposed to air, while anode faces the outside and is exposed to the surrounding soil matrix. This kind of system maximizes the compactness of the reactor, decreases the electrode spacing and reduces intrinsic losses, with a consequent improvement of electron and mass transfer [105]. Lu and colleagues inserted tubular MFCs with carbon cloth anode or biochar anode into raw water-saturated soils containing petroleum hydrocarbons. A biochar anode showed better performance for diesel degradation and current output than a carbon cloth anode, due to higher adsorption capability that provided more substrates for microbes and facilitated hydrocarbon diffusion from soil matrix towards the anode. Results show that, within 1 cm from the anode, total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) removal rate was almost double (63.5–78.7%) than that in the open circuit positive controls (37.6–43.4%) during a period of 64 days [55]. This study showed that the estimated radius of influence (ROI) gradually expanded from the electrode surface, as the total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) degradation increased overtime at a distance of 5 cm from the anode. The same tubular configuration (but using carbon felt as anode) was used in another study, where authors investigated how soil type and water saturation level affected the performance of bioelectrochemical remediation [68]. Two column-type MFC modules were installed into a 50-L pilot scale reactor packed with diesel-contaminated soils to investigate the enhancement of passive biodegradation of petroleum compounds [18]. By using low-cost electrodes such as biochar and graphite granule as non-exhaustible solid-state electron acceptors, the results show that 82.1–89.7% of TPH was degraded after 120 days across 1–34 cm radius of influence (ROI) from the modules. The system did not consume any chemical or energy but instead produced 70.4 ± 0.2 mA/m² of electrical current. This pilot scale MFC was designed to easily integrate with existing groundwater monitoring wells or piezometers, and the electricity produced could provide information about the contaminant degradation profile and even power other sensors.

Increasing anode sizes and improving contact of surface areas between the anode and the soil were found lightening limitation of mass transfers. In this respect, several MET designs such as U-type reactors with four pairs of air cathodes and anodes (Fig. 5C) [13] and multi-

Fig. 5. Reactor configurations of soil electrobioremediation systems: A) insertion-type [114]; B) tubular or column-type [18,55,68,75]; C) U-tube [13]; D) multi-anode [69,74,77]; E) graphite rod [66].

anode reactors with three layers of anodes system and one air cathode (Fig. 5D) [69,74,77] were applied in soil remediation.

By applying U-tube microbial fuel cells (MFCs), the degradation rate of petroleum hydrocarbons close to the anode (<1 cm) was doubled, i.e. from 6.9% (open circuit control) to 15.2% with simultaneous 125 Coulombs of charge output (with maximum power density of 0.85 mW/m²) in the tested period (25 days) [13]. Hydrocarbons fingerprinting analysis showed that the degradation rate of both alkanes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) was accelerated. Anyway, this study found the effect of U-shape MET only placed on the soil close to anode (ROI < 1 cm) and the efficiency decreased with larger ROI.

Multilayer anodes can be used to extend working range [72]. Using a three-anodes (carbon meshes) system with activated carbon as the cathodic catalyst, 918 Coulombs were transferred during 180 days in aged saline soil. The degradation of both polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and n-alkanes were accelerated in each layer compared to the open circuit control. The net biodegradation rates of TPH, 16 priority PAHs and total n-alkanes (C8–C40) were 18%, 36% and 29%, respectively.

Zhang and co-authors developed air–cathode MFCs with anodes horizontally arranged (HA) and vertically arranged (VA) for in situ soil bioremediation coupled to electrical energy production [74] (Fig. 5D). The HA demonstrated a superior performance compared with VA for removal of hydrocarbons. Up to 12.5% of TPH was removed in HA after 135 days, which was 50.6% higher than that in VA (8.3%) and 95.3% higher than that in the open circuit control (6.4%). Hydrocarbon fingerprint analysis showed that the degradation rates of both alkanes and PAHs in HA were higher than those in VA. Lower mass transport resistance in the HA than that of the VA seems to result in more power and more TPH degradation.

In a multi-anode (horizontal) soil MFC with the addition of glucose, the charge output was enhanced by 262%, and the total petroleum hydrocarbon degradation rate increased by 200% [69]. According to the

increased dehydrogenase and polyphenol oxidase activities, the exogenous glucose substantially activated microbial communities involved in hydrocarbon degradation. In a similar multi-anode MFC, sand amendment can also enhance soil porosity, decrease ohmic resistance (by 46%) and increase TPH degradation (up to 268%) [77].

A simplified soil MFC was also proposed, assembled with an anode of graphite rod and an activated carbon air–cathode (Fig. 5E) [66]. In this MFC, soil contaminated with petroleum hydrocarbon was mixed with carbon fibers, lowering the resistance of soil. The effective range of remediation and the bioelectricity recovery was extended from 6 to 20 cm with the same area of air–cathode.

All of these configurations demonstrated a significant enhancement of PH degradation in closed circuit condition as compared to the OCP. The potentials that were measured across external resistors between 100 and 1000 Ω range from 73 to 457 mV [13,55,62,66,69,70,72,74]. Power densities typically vary between 0.85 and 225 mW/m² (Table 1).

However, in view of a full-scale application the system setup needs to be easy to implement on field. Although a multi anode configuration can extend the working range of soil MFC, this setting requires implementing more electrodes in parallel with distances of several centimeters, which is unfavorable in field application. For this reason, column or tubular configurations seems to be better candidates in near-future installations [96].

5.2. Operational parameters

To start with, an unexpected finding is that electrobioremediation technologies have been successfully applied to PH-contaminated soils characterized by a broad range of electric conductivities, spanning from 0.2 mS/cm (i.e., non-saline soils) up to nearly 6 mS/cm (i.e., slightly saline soils), as shown in Fig. 6. Interestingly, although in some cases the treatment capacity was enhanced by increasing soil conductivity (e.g., through addition of water or salts), in many other studies this was not

Fig. 6. Apparent effect of soil conductivity on the fold increase of PH removal in MET-based systems relative to open circuit controls.

the case, thereby indicating that this parameter alone cannot be a sufficient predictor of PH-biodegradation success. Indeed, as shown in Fig. 6, the fold of increase of treatment capacity of MET-based systems relative to Open Circuit Control (OCP) did not show any positive correlation with soil conductivity. Instead, a slightly negative correlation was apparently observed, as also documented in previous studies [55].

Overall, it is apparent that factors other than electrical conductivity are likely to play a major role, such as the slow activation and biodegradation of PH under anaerobic conditions, the low contaminant bioavailability due to the binding of non-polar contaminants onto the organic constituents of the soil, and the poor mass transport properties of the systems as a whole. As far as these latter properties are concerned, soil texture and particularly soil hydraulic conductivity appear to be key parameters whose proper management, for instance through the addition of sand to the contaminated soil, can have a positive impact on treatment capacity.

Another parameter that has a major impact on the outcome of the system performances is the duration of the experimentation. As it can be observed in Table 1, the duration of the published trials varied between 14 and 250 days. However, on average they lasted 131 days, with 73% of the studies ranging from 110 and 250 days. That is usually the time needed by the system to remove the degradable fraction of the contaminants.

All experiments were conducted under batch or fed-batch regime within MET and at room temperature (in the range 20–30 °C). Initial hydrocarbon concentrations range from 11 to 83 g TPH/kg of dry matter in soils contaminated by aged petroleum hydrocarbons, and 6–12 g TPH/kg of dry matter in soils spiked with diesel (Table 1). Bioremediation performance of MET is evaluated considering the removal of hydrocarbons in terms of TPH (Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons), but some studies assess the effect of the bioelectrochemical process on specific classes of hydrocarbons, such as alkanes and aromatics [62,65,66]. Taken as a whole, it is apparent that most of the available literature on soil electrobioremediation is still largely based on experiments carried out at lab-scale, under experimental conditions which are only partially representative of those occurring at real contaminated sites. While the performance of MET systems at temperatures lower than 20 °C can be probably extrapolated with good accuracy from data collected at room temperatures using empirical correlations, the lack of longer-term experiments carried out also at lower contaminant concentrations makes the likely outcome of field-scale soil electrobioremediation processes more difficult to predict. Clearly, further experimental work is needed to address these issues.

5.3. Field application: Radius of influence (ROI) and scalability issues

In spite of the continued research efforts and the study of diverse

MET configurations and operational conditions, several issues still hamper the field applicability and scalability of this technology. To date, reactor-working volumes ranged between laboratory scale (0.216 – 4.8 L) and pilot scale (50 L) (Table 1) but most of the research studies has been conducted in the laboratory, with reactors smaller than 1 L. Moreover, the radius of influence (ROI) of soil electrobioremediation systems is typically <50 cm (Fig. 7). The scaling-up and extension of the ROI are between the most important aspects to consider before applying METs to the remediation of soils [11]. The ROI can be influenced by both the bioelectrocatalytic reaction rate and the transport rate of the contaminant through the soil matrix in terms of diffusion, migration and convection. If the reaction rate is significantly higher than the transport rate, it means that the movement of the contaminant in the matrix is limiting the process. Vice versa, if the transport rate is higher, the process is limited by the reaction kinetic. The interplay between these two phenomena can be synthetically expressed by the dimensionless Damköhler number, which is defined as the ratio between the maximum value of the reaction rate and the maximum value of mass transport rate in the process [115]. In order to improve the reaction rate, features like the electrodic material, the biofilm composition and the electrode spacing should be optimized, and the ohmic losses of the system should be minimized. Along this line, the possibility to exploit the recently discovered capability of microorganisms to engage in long-distance interspecies electron transfer via conductive materials (e.g., biochar), minerals (e.g., iron oxides), diffusible redox mediators (e.g., quinone/hydroquinone moieties) or perhaps by stimulating the growth of filamentous “cable” bacteria in the soil, all represent promising and exciting research avenues. On the other hand, the transport rate can be affected by the low mobility of contaminant inside the soil matrix and/or adsorption phenomena. This can be tackled by generating a convective movement of the liquid phase, using for example a groundwater circulation well. Overall, this issue deserves further research efforts to be properly addressed, as it has a critical impact on the economic viability and competitiveness of this innovative technology and in turn on its likelihood of commercial deployment.

6. Conclusion

This review paper has analyzed the rapidly expanding scientific literature dealing with MET-based soil remediation, in order to systemize the relevance of key operational and environmental parameters on treatment performance.

The main finding of this work can be summarized as follows:

Fig. 7. Apparent effect of distance from the anode on the fold increase of PH removal in MET-based systems relative to open circuit controls, assuming a linear relationship.

1. The vast majority of studies was conducted using air–cathode MFCs, since they seem to be the most sustainable and cost-effective setups for long-term operations
2. Tubular (or column type) systems seem to be the best candidates for field application, since their geometry decreases the electrode spacing and reduces ohmic losses. Moreover, due to their shape, they can be easily installed in existing facilities such as groundwater piezometers and monitoring wells.
3. Interestingly, the change in soil conductivity does not seem to have a strong impact on the removal of PHs. Therefore, this analysis indicates that other factors are likely to play a major role, like for example bioactivation and biodegradation rates of PHs under anaerobic conditions, contaminant bioavailability and mass transport limitations.
4. The radius of influence of electrodes is usually <50 cm, which could be a limiting factor for the up-scaling of the process. To overcome this issue, further research should address the optimization of the bioelectrocatalytic reaction rate and the improvement of the mass transport in the soil matrix.
5. Only an extremely limited number of studies have successfully tested soil electroremediation technologies at the pilot scale. This type of investigation is extremely important to confirm results obtained at the laboratory-scale under more controlled, yet often far-less representative, conditions as well as to catalyze the commercial, societal, and administrative interest of potential stakeholders.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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